

A predictive multiscale model of in-stent restenosis in femoral arteries: linking hemodynamics and gene expression with an agent-based model of cellular dynamics

- Supplementary Materials -

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Supplementary methods

Morphing procedure

The morphing procedure was adopted to virtually implant the stent in the vessel geometry and obtain a perfect adherence between the stent and the lumen surface. The procedure consisted in the following steps: (i) the undeformed stent model was aligned with the vessel axis; (ii) the nodes of the stent mesh (i.e., the *domain*) were selected as object to be morphed; (iii) the morphing surface was generated, consisting in a cylindrical surface coaxial with the stent; (iv) the stent axis was selected for the morphing calculation; and (v) the vessel surface was identified as *destination* surface.

CFD solver settings

The *pressure-based coupled scheme* was the solver used for the CFD simulation in the present work. *Least square cell-based, second order* and *second order upwind* schemes were adopted for the spatial discretization of the gradient, the pressure and the momentum, respectively. The Courant number was set equal to 50 and relaxation factors of 0.3 were assumed for the pressure and momentum.

Computation of the surrogate model outputs

The lumen area of the stented portion was obtained by: (i) measuring the lumen area of 42 evenly spaced cross-sections (1 mm); (ii) dividing the 42 cross-sections in 7 sectors (decorrelation length of 6 mm [1]); (iii) computing the lumen area of each sector as median lumen area of the 6 contained cross-sections; and (iv) computing the lumen area of the stented portion as median lumen area of the 7 sectors. The normalized intimal ECM/SMC ratio was obtained by computing the median over the 9 ABM configurations (selected among the 3 repetitions) of the intimal ECM/SMC ratio at 1 month normalized on the initial value.

Calibration: genetic algorithm

The non-dominated sorting genetic algorithm (NSGA-II) [2,3] was adopted in Matlab to find the optimal solution. The parameters set for the genetic algorithm optimization were the following: a population of 200 individuals, a crossover fraction of 0.8, a binary tournament selection, a Gaussian mutation and a maximum number of 1200 generations.

Post-print

Supplementary figures

Supplementary Figure S1. Representation of the variable $D(WSS)$, accounting for the impact of the wall shear stress (WSS) on the level of endothelial dysfunction.

Post-print

Supplementary Figure S2. Formulation of the gene expression-based input (GE_{input}). A) The gene expression (GE) of 3 out of 34 clusters that were found to be significantly differentially expressed between success and failure groups are shown. The green curve represents the average curve of the success group, while the red one that of the failure group. All the gene expression curves were log2-transformed, namely the displayed value of gene expression was computed as $GE(t) = \log_2 \left(\frac{v(t)}{v(t_0)} \right)$, where $v(t)$ is the measured gene expression level at time t and $v(t_0)$ is the pre-operative gene expression level. B) Representation of the sigmoid-shaped function used to compute the weight w for each cluster, where Δ_5 and $\Delta_{8,24}$ are the differences between the patient-specific curve and average success curve for the clusters 5, 8 and 24.

Supplementary Figure S3. Surrogate model validation. A) Leave-one-out standardized cross validated residual (SCVR) values of the 1-month lumen area and normalized intimal extracellular matrix / smooth muscle cell ratio ($\text{ECM}/\text{SMC}_{\text{ratio_int}}$). B) SCVR values of the 1-month lumen area and normalized $\text{ECM}/\text{SMC}_{\text{ratio_int}}$ for 10 additional cases (not used for the surrogate model construction).

Supplementary Figure S4. Agent-based model (ABM) outputs at 1 month obtained from 3 repetitions of the ABM simulation for 3 explanatory planes of the stented region of the patient-specific superficial femoral artery model. On the left, the wall shear stress (WSS) contour of the stented portion is shown and, on the right, the 3 1-month ABM outputs (a, b, c) of planes 1, 5 and 9 are illustrated.

Supplementary video

Results of the calibrated framework for 3 explanatory planes of the stented region of the patient-specific superficial femoral artery model. On the left, the wall shear stress (WSS) contour of the stented portion is shown, and, on the right, the temporal evolution of the agent-based models (ABM) of 3 explanatory planes (plane 1, plane 5 and plane 9) along 1 simulated month (day 0, day 5, day 10, day 15, day 20, day 25 and day 30). **For each** ABM plane, the results were retrieved from 1 out of 3 ABM simulations, namely the one presenting the lumen configuration minimizing the root mean square deviation, as detailed in Section 2.1.5.

References

1. Colombo M, He Y, Corti A, Gallo D, Casarin S, Rozowsky JM, Migliavacca F, Berceci S, Chiastra C. 2021 Baseline local hemodynamics as predictor of lumen remodeling at 1-year follow-up in stented superficial femoral arteries. *Sci. Rep.* **11**, 1613. (doi:10.1038/s41598-020-80681-8)
2. Deb K, Pratap A, Agarwal S, Meyarivan T. 2002 A fast and elitist multiobjective genetic algorithm: NSGA-II. *IEEE Trans. Evol. Comput.* **6**, 182–197. (doi:10.1109/4235.996017)
3. Carbonaro D, Gallo D, Morbiducci U, Audenino A, Chiastra C. 2021 In silico biomechanical design of the metal frame of transcatheter aortic valves: multi-objective shape and cross-sectional size optimization. *Struct. Multidiscip. Optim.* (doi:10.1007/s00158-021-02944-w)